

RESEARCH AND OBSERVATION AT THE MAIDANAK OBSERVATORY IN THE FRAMEWORK OF INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION

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One of the current modern areas of astrophysics is the observation and research of gravitational lensed quasars (GLQs). These unique objects, observed exclusively on a cosmic scale, make it possible to directly estimate the Hubble constant H_0 , calculate the time delay in the GLQ, study the effects of microlensing, modeling the distribution of baryonic and dark matter in lensing galaxies, and estimate the size of a quasar black hole.

However, such studies require the best possible angular resolution and long-term monitoring observations with a seeing quality of $\sim 1''$. As an example, observations at the Maidanak Observatory of the Ulugh Beg Astronomical Institute (UBAI) makes possible to measure the time delay in the GLQs. Also, high-quality images from the Hubble Space Telescope (HST) and spectroscopy from the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) are needed to model the GLQ. Such comprehensive studies of GLQs are possible only within the framework of international scientific cooperation. Such cooperation is an agreement between the Ulugh Beg Astronomical Institute (UBAI) and the Laboratory of Astrophysics Ecole Polytechnique Federale of Lausanne (EPFL).

As part of this collaboration between UBAI and EPFL at the Maidanak Observatory on the 1.5m AZT-22 telescope since 2018 monitoring observations of GLQ SDSS J1721+8842, SDSS J1433+6007 and SDSS J2145+6345 are being carried out. A specialized numerical MCS deconvolution method is used to reductions of GLQ images. This method makes it possible to significantly increase the angular resolution, as well as to separate the lensed components of the GLQ for photometry and time delay calculations.

Fig.1. Images of the GLQ SDSS J1721+8842 from the Maidanak observatory with the results of reductions in comparison with the HST and the light curve for 2018-2023.

Other field of researches at the Maidanak Observatory requires application of modern digital control methods and the digital CCD imaging from telescopes, as well as the ability to analyze images in real time, can significantly improve the quality and quantity of astronomical observations within the framework of international agreements. One of such agreements is an international project with the Yunnan Observatory (China) and UBAI for BVRI monitoring observations of special double interacting stars at the Maidanak Observatory. The cooperation is carried out within the framework of the allocated grant from the Ministry of Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan AL-5921122128 “Research and observations of special eclipsing binary systems according to LAMOST data on telescopes of Uzbekistan and China”.

At the Astronomical Institute for the ZEISS-600-East telescope at the Maidanak Observatory, a digital precision correction system CS-ET-60 was developed and implemented. This made it possible to improve the quality of observations of double stars within the framework of an international project, as well as to resolve the task of remote control of the telescope’s precise correction from a computer.

Fig.2. Field of stars long 300 sec. exposures from the Zeiss-600-East telescope and phase BVRI light curves of 2023 year monitoring observations of the eclipsing binary star system TIC122070918.

Increasing the efficiency and speed of observations under the international project requires further modernization of the telescope through the development of computer-aided design (CAD) methods and 3-D modeling of innovative mechanical and electronic components and using modern technologies. This will make possible the subsequent introduction of modern IT technologies for complete remote control of telescopes. The application of such innovative digital systems will also significantly increase the speed of pointing telescopes to astronomical objects and analyze CCD image data in real time.